

SYNTHESIS, COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THERMAL AND MICROWAVE CURED EPON-862/CNFs NANOCOMPOSITES

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SUMMARY

The main focus of this research is to compare the microwave heating and conventional thermal processing by studying the thermal and mechanical properties of neat epon-862 epoxy resin and carbon nanofiber (CNFs) infused epon-862 nanocomposites. Other than drastic decrease in processing time the microwave processing of epon862+0.3% CNFs shown an increase of 27.51%, 25.98% and 28.63% respectively for flexure modulus, flexure strength and flexure strain at failure as compared to neat epon862/CNFs thermal processing

Keywords Microwave curing; CNFs; Flexural Properties

INTRODUCTION

There is an ever increasing demand of industrial applications of high-performance structural adhesives. Due to the increasing demand of composite structures, especially in aerospace industry is urged to accelerate the production speed and reduce the composite product costs. Epoxy based resins are extensively used in various composite industries and every day life since their first discovery in 1936 by Dr. Pierre Castan of Switzerland and Dr. S.O. Greenlee of the United States. In general these epoxy resin are known for their excellent adhesion, chemical and heat resistance, excellent mechanical and electrical insulating properties. They are typically two component systems and cured at room temperature or at high temperature but both types of curing take prolong times like one or two days [1]. The high temperature cured epoxies are more heat and chemical resistant than cured at room temperature [2]. For these reasons, it is of great interest to study the rapid curing process influences the cure behavior of composites comparing with the conventional slow production. Over the last five decades the applications of microwave radiation has been increased tremendously in various scientific research fields [2, 3]. The application of microwave heating in composite materials processing is very limited because of the complexity involved in heat absorption of epoxies and other components at different rates simultaneously [4,5].

Field of nanotechnology is still unrefined in certain aspects, curing is one of them. New tests bring out new breakthrough and there are avenues in nanotechnology which have not been discovered yet. The manufacturing and curing of nacocomposites is one area of major research. Recent studies have shown that nanocomposites exhibit remarkable improvements in stiffness, strength, physio-chemical and thermal properties without

compromising on density, toughness or processibility compared to their micro- and macro-composite counterparts as shown by Alexander et al. [6]. The conventional method followed is room temperature curing which is time consuming. This technology cannot meet the constrain laid down by cost concerns due to high budgets, and therefore, time is a major constraint. The longer it takes to complete a project, the more expensive it becomes. Alternate curing method have been tried and tested for quite some time now. Four alternative curing technique already used and these are-UV rays, Gamma rays, Electron Beam and Microwave [7, 8].

Curing using UV light has limited application due to its poor penetrability and limited dose rate it can not cure thick materials [9]. Gamma rays induced radiation hazard and environmental issues. The most prominent alternatives suggested are Electron Beam (EB) and Microwave heating [10]. Electron Beam curing though efficient and fast unfortunately requires high capital cost for initial setup [11]. It has some other drawbacks like low glass transition temperature (or low service temperature), low fracture toughness, and high shrinkage when cured [12].

Microwave curing, therefore, is the more economically feasible alternative and is remarkably energy efficient [13-15]. Microwave heating is unique in the fact that heat is generated in the specimen rather than externally transferred. The potential for microwave curing stems from the fact that there are no major drawbacks for the method. The curing of nanoparticles infused epoxy using microwaves is a relatively unexplored area of research. A novel method has to be formulated from testing different conditions of cure selecting from factors like power level of microwave, time to cure, percentage of nanoparticles infusion, method of infusion and finally relative cost than other technique. In the current study, carbon nanofiber infused nanocomposites were prepared with different weight percentage of nanofiber by two alternative method one is thermally curing and post curing (TC & TPC) and another is microwave curing (MWC) and tested for their thermal and mechanical properties.

EXPERIMENTAL

Material Selection and Specimen Fabrication

In the current study, epon-862 epoxy resin was purchased from Miller Stephenson Chemical Company. It is a two part epoxy system. Part A is Epon-862 (Diglycidyle Ether of Bisphenol-F) and Part-B is Epicure W (Aromatic Amine based curing agent). The density of epon-862 is ~1.2003gm/cc and viscosity of Part A: 250-450 cps and Part B: 100-300 cps @ room temperature. The manufactures suggested mixing ratio of epon-862 is Part A (100): Part B (26.4) by weight and cured at 120°C for 4 hours, followed by post curing at 170°C for another 4 hours. Carbon nanofibers (CNFs) used in this study was purchased from Applied Science Inc, USA. These CNFs are HT-grade pyrograf-III with a purity of 95% and density of 1.95 g/cm³, average out side diameter of 100-200 nm, and length of 10-40 μm.

The CNFs were dispersed through acoustic cavitations process. Part-A was selected for infusion of CNFs since this part is less reactive to ultrasound irradiation. Pre-calculated

amount of CNFs and part A were carefully weighed and mixed together in a suitable beaker. Dispersion was then carried out through a *Sonics Vibra Cell* Ultrasonic Liquid Processor (Ti-horn, 20 kHz, 100W/cm²) at 50% of amplitude for 15 minutes. In order to avoid a temperature increase during the sonication process, external cooling was employed by submerging the mixing beaker in a thermostatic bath at 10°C for the entire period of the ultrasound irradiation. Once the irradiation was completed, part B was mixed to the modified part A at a ratio of 100:26.4 and allowed to mix together using a THINKY hybrid de-foaming mixture ARE-250 at 2000 rpm for 15 minutes. In this technique the material container is set at 45 degrees angle and revolves and rotates (2000 rpm) at the same time. Dual centrifugal forces were given to the material that keep pressing material to outward and down along with the slope of inner wall of container. The trapped air and initial reaction volatiles were removed from the mixture by using the high vacuum. Finally the mixture is cured using a 2.45GHz (Microwave Processing Oven BP210) microwave oven for only 10 minutes instead of 8 hours for conventional oven heating (Curing schedule is 4 hrs @ 120 °C and Post curing @ 170 °C for 4hrs). Thermal and Mechanical tests were performed for all the sample including thermally cured and microwave cured and finally samples were prepared for subsequent tests. A controlled neat epoxy was cured by following the same manufacturing procedure without CNFs.

Characterization techniques

Thermogravimetric

Thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of various specimens was carried out under nitrogen gas atmosphere on a Mettler Toledo TGA/SDTA 851° apparatus. The samples were cut into small pieces 10-20 mg using a surgical blade. The TGA measurements were carried out from 30°C to 800°C at a heating rate of 10°C/minute. Differential scanning calorimetric (DSC) experiments were carried out using a Mettler Toledo DSC 822° from 30°C to 300°C at a heating rate of 10°C/minute under nitrogen atmosphere.

Flexural Test

Flexure tests were performed using the Zwick/Roell test machine with 2.5 kN load cell at a cross head speed of 2 mm/min. The tests were performed according to ASTM D 790-07. Flexural properties such as flexural strength and modulus were determined. In this test, beam specimens of rectangular cross section were loaded in a three-point bending mode. Six samples were tested for each nanofiber loading. Beam specimens of dimension: thickness ~ 4.5 mm, width ~ 12.5 mm, span length 70 mm were cut from composites disk using a high speed diamond cutter and loaded under three point bending. This method was used to determine flexural strength and modulus of elasticity of nanofiber infused nanoparticles.

Quasi-Static Compression

In order to study the compression response, the specimens were tested in the thickness direction using servo-hydraulically controlled Material Testing System MTS-810. An ASTM C365-57 standard was followed for the quasistatic compression test. The size of test specimens was 12.7 mm X 12.7 mm X 12.7 mm. The capacity of the MTS machine is approximately 10KN. To maintain evenly distributed compressive loading, each specimen was sanded and polished with high accuracy so that the opposite faces were parallel to one another. A software Test Ware-SX was used to develop a program, which controlled the test conditions and recorded both the load and crosshead displacement data. The load-deflection data recorded by the data acquisition system was converted to stress–strain curves.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The TGA analysis was carried out to study the thermal behavior of neat and nanocomposites cured with microwave and oven heating. Thermal decomposition of cross linked polymers preferentially takes place via a chemical conversion of side chains. Nanoparticles, which have a higher heat absorbing capacity, can help in improving the degradation temperature of the epoxy. In this case the relatively small amount of CNFs may not be sufficient to alter the chemistry of the epoxy, thereby resulting in almost the same decomposition temperature. Table 1 is summarized the decomposition temperature and percentage of residue for all samples with two different routes of curing. Bond breaking inside the polymer matrix requires a large amount of energy.

Table 1: Decomposition temperature and residue of Epon-862/ CNFs.

Sample	TC & TPC		MWC	
	Decomp. Temp., (°C)	Residue, (%)	Decomp. Temp., (°C)	Residue, (%)
Neat Epon862	388.98	3.82	389.38	14.52
Epon862+0.1% CNF	387.74	8.70	388.61	14.08
Epon862+0.2% CNF	387.73	11.85	388.79	14.03
Epon862+0.3% CNF	387.83	15.59	388.32	14.53
Epon862+0.4% CNF	389.21	13.14	389.11	14.59

Flexural Analysis

A Flexure tests produce a tensile stress in the convex side of the specimen and compression stress in the concave side. This creates an area of shear stress along the midline. Flexure test measures the force required to bend a specimen under 3 point loading condition. In a 3-point test the area of uniform stress is quite small and point concentrated under the center loading point

Figure. 1. Combined Flexural Stress- Strain graphs of neat and CNFs infused Epon-862 with different loading of CNFs (a) Thermally cured and post cure (b) Microwave cure.

Figure 1(a) is the flexural graphs of thermally cured and post cured neat and different percentages CNFs-filled epon862 nanocomposites. From the above graphs it clear that flexure modulus and strength of the composites increased with the addition of CNF nanoparticles with respect to neat counterparts. Addition of nanoparticles up to a specific concentration decreased the mobility of the cross linking in the polymer and increased the mechanical and thermal properties by shifting from relatively ductile to brittle one [16, 17]. For thermal curing it did not show any saturation concentration up to 0.4% CNFs addition.

Table 2: Combined Flexure strength values of neat and CNFs filled Epon-862.

Sample Name	Flexure strength in MPa	
	TC & TPC	MWC
Neat Epon862	101.57	118.81
Epon862+0.1% CNF	109.26	121.44
Epon862+0.2% CNF	117.47	123.53
Epon862+0.3% CNF	123.02	127.96
Epon862+0.4% CNT	130.71	119.48

Flexural graphs of microwave cured neat and different percentages CNFs-filled epon862 nanocomposites are shown in Figure 1 (b). This figure is also showing the similar trend of previous figure that means with the addition of nanoparticles flexure modulus and strength increased up to 0.3% CNFs (3.29GPa and 127.96MPa) loading . For 0.4% CNFs loading modulus and strength both drastically decreased (2.90GPa and 119.48MPa) because of over soldering effect [18]. The welding mechanism is thought to involve the wetting of the CNFs by the surrounding polymer melt; a nanometer-sized melted polymer region is likely formed around the nanoparticles due to the dissipation of heat from the CNFs to polymer. This local melting leads to physical intercalation of

the CNFs and the polymers and yielding a bonding strength two order of magnitude higher than that obtained for polymer bonded together by epoxy adhesive

Table 3: Combined strain at failure values of neat and CNFs filled Epon-862

Sample Name	Flexure strain at failure, in %	
	TC & TPC	MWC
Neat Epon862	8.80	9.35
Epon862+0.1% CNF	8.74	10.38
Epon862+0.2% CNF	8.41	11.00
Epon862+0.3% CNF	8.14	11.32
Epon862+0.4% CNT	7.80	6.38

The welding mechanism is effective when the dispersion of nanoparticles good enough. If the dispersion of nanoparticles is not good enough, produce small agglomeration then welding mechanism act as a negative effect. Small agglomeration may produce sufficient heat to cross the decomposition temperature of the nanocomposites by absorbing microwave radiation and these localized over heating around the small agglomeration damaged the bonding properties of the matrix and finally reduced thermal and mechanical properties of the nanocomposites [18]. Table 2 and Table 3 summarize the flexural properties of neat and CNFs-filled epon862 with two different routes of curing. Microwave curing (MWC) showed the better properties than Thermally cure and post cure (TC & TPC). Epon862+0.3%CNFs, MWC showed 27.51% , 25.98% and 28.63% improvement in flexure modulus, flexure strength and flexure strain at failure respectively than neat thermally cured and post cure nanocomposites.

Compression Analysis

Compression test carried out to measure the load carrying capacity of a material before fracture. It can be seen that stress-strain curves has two major distinct phases – an initial elastic response and a protracted plateau. The elastic region is controlled by the stretching of the epoxy polymer. The stress plateau is associated with the time taken to form matrix cracking and crack propagation followed by barreling/bulging and increase in the lateral dimension of the rectangular samples.

Table 4: Combined compression modulus values of neat and CNFs filled Epon-862

Sample Name	Compression modulus in GPa	
	TC & TPC	MWC
Neat Epon862	1.960	2.238
Epon862+0.1% CNF	2.075	2.391
Epon862+0.2% CNF	2.172	2.451
Epon862+0.3% CNF	2.275	2.527
Epon862+0.4% CNF	2.313	2.701

Table 5: Combined compression modulus values of neat and CNFs filled Epon-862

Sample Name	Compression Strength in MPa	
	TC & TPC	MWC
Neat Epon862	113.94	114.44
Epon862+0.1% CNF	115.66	117.73
Epon862+0.2% CNF	117.07	119.42
Epon862+0.3% CNF	118.18	121.30
Epon862+0.4% CNF	120.04	118.04

From the Figure 2(a) it is clear that the addition of nanoparticles to Epon-826 polymer, the composites modulus and strength increased at the cost of elongation. For thermally cured and post cured it did not show any saturation percentage up to 0.4% CNFs addition. The Figure 2 (b) also show similar trend up to 0.3% CNs addition that means with the addition of nanoparticles, composites compression modulus and strength increased because addition of nanoparticles up to a specific concentration decreased the

Figure 2: Combined Stress- Strain graphs of neat and CNFs filled epon862 with different loading of CNFs (a) Thermally cured and post cure (b) Microwave cure.

mobility of the cross-linking network in the polymer and increased the thermal and mechanical properties [16, 17,]. Beyond that specific percentage, addition of particles creates agglomeration that deteriorates the composites property. Here microwave cured 0.3% CNFs showed the best property because of welding mechanism [18]. Welding mechanism has negative effect if dispersion of nanoparticles is not occurred correctly. In the case of 0.4% CNFs loading small agglomeration damaged the welding phenomena but still restrict the mobility of cross-linked network that is why modulus is

increased but strength is decreased. In the case of 0.3% CNFs loading 28.93% compression modulus and 6.46% compression strength increased with respect to neat thermal curing and post curing. Table 4 and Table 5 summarize the compression properties of neat and CNFs-filled Epon-862 with two different routes of curing. Microwave curing (MWC) showed the better properties than thermally cure and post cure (TC & TPC). Epon862+0.3%CNFs showed 28.93% and 6.45% improvement in compression modulus and compression strength respectively than neat thermally cured and post cure nanocomposites.

CONCLUSIONS

In this study we have shown that CNFs infusion had a positive effect on thermal and mechanical properties of the nanocomposites up to a specific concentration (~0.3% CNFs). For MWC samples the flexural properties improved for Epon862+0.3%CNFs 27.51%, 25.98% and 28.63% improvement in flexure modulus, flexure strength and flexure strain at failure respectively as compared to the neat thermally cured and post cure. The compressive property results of MWC samples of Epon862+0.3%CNFs MWC showed 28.93% and 6.45% improvement in compression modulus and compression strength respectively than neat thermally cured and post cure.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Authors would like to thank the NSF-PREM, CREST and RISE for supporting this research.

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